

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IMPLEMENTATION OF A DAILY TELEMETRY RENEWAL PROTOCOL: A
QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Continuous electrocardiographic monitoring is currently standard practice for all patients with acute coronary syndromes. Although the American Heart Association (AHA) published a set of evidence-based practice standards for telemetry utilization, it is not widely used, resulting in telemetry overuse. Overmonitoring is financially costly and can lead to alarm fatigue and ultimately cause patient harm. The purpose of this project was to develop, implement and evaluate a provider-led, AHA daily telemetry renewal protocol at a community hospital to decrease unnecessary telemetry use. After a retrospective chart review to identify the unit with the highest days of telemetry use, a protocol was implemented on a neuroscience unit. One hundred fifty-five patients were evaluated over a 15-day period. Patients were mostly male and ranged in age from 28-99 years of age with the average age of 64 years. The percentage of patients not meeting the protocol ranged from 14%-56%. Once evaluated, the providers were asked to re-evaluate the patients need for telemetry. Telemetry use was significantly decreased by 17.9%. The main rationale providers gave for not discontinuing telemetry was the age of the patient and agitation. In this project, an AHA derived telemetry use protocol was effective in reducing the number of patients being monitored. Providers reluctant to discontinue telemetry need for non-cardiac reasons need to identify other strategies for patient safety.

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BACKGROUND

The electrocardiographic (ECG) monitor is an inpatient tool that allows continuous cardiac monitoring of critical patients; it can detect life-threatening arrhythmias associated with cardiovascular disease and promptly alert clinicians to intervene. Telemetry, or continuous ECG monitoring is currently standard practice for all patients with acute coronary syndromes (Braunwald, 2012). In 2004, the American Heart Association (AHA) published a set of evidence-based practice standards for inpatient ECG monitoring that outlined specific criteria for telemetry indication and duration (Drew et al., 2017). Despite the support of the American College of Cardiology, and campaign efforts of the American Board of Internal Medicine Foundation in promoting protocol-based practice, AHA's guideline compliance is low, resulting in widespread telemetry overuse (Chen et al., 2017). Multiple studies from the last ten years found that up to 40% of admitted telemetry patients did not meet inpatient telemetry criteria (Chen et al., 2017; Dressler et al., 2014; Kanwar, Fares, Minnick, Rosman, & Saravolatz, 2008).

Inappropriate telemetry use is expensive and labor-intensive; it can cost an average-sized hospital 100 nursing hours per patient, and up to \$250,000 extra per year (Chen et al., 2017). Rizvi et al. (2017) estimated the cost of daily telemetry to be approximately \$1,400 per patient. Telemetry maintenance tasks such as regular rhythm analysis increase nursing burden and distract clinicians from other aspects of patient care (Feder & Funk, 2013). The shortage of inpatient telemetry beds delays hospital throughput and increases overcrowding in the emergency room (Bailey et al., 2005). A patient being inappropriately monitored occupies the resources that may potentially save

the life of an acutely-ill cardiac patient. Telemetry over-prescription can lead to unnecessary interventions such as cardiac catheterization and implantable cardioverter defibrillator placement (Patel, 2016).

Overmonitoring also leads to alarm fatigue, a phenomenon where nurses who are exposed to a high number of alarms become desensitized and fail to recognize and respond to sentinel alerts (Keller, 2012). Alarm fatigue leads to patient deaths. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) found 566 deaths related to alarms from 2005 to 2008 (Food and Drug Administration, 2010), and the Joint Commission (2013) found 98 sentinel events and 80 deaths directly related to alarm fatigue. Sentinel events are defined by the Joint Commission (2009) as unexpected patient events in the healthcare setting that leads to serious injury or death that is unrelated to the natural course of patients' illnesses. Telemetry gives clinicians a false sense of security. Instead of physically assessing the patient, many nurses rely on the monitors; this is a dangerous practice because no machines should replace regular nursing assessment.

Electrocardiographic monitors produce a high number of false alarms, and are ineffective in differentiating clinically significant events (Salas-Boni, Bai, Harris, Drew, & Hu, 2014). Gross, Dahl & Nielsen (2011) found that only 34% of alarms on a subacute medical surgical unit corresponded to critical events. Another study that looked at telemetry validity in acute stroke patients showed that less than 1% of total alarms correlated with acute life-threatening events (Kurka et al., 2014). Additionally, responding to non-actionable alarms interrupts nursing workflow, increases the likelihood of clinical errors, and leads to nurse burnout (Whalen et al., 2014). In a time of

increasing healthcare costs and nursing shortage, decreasing inappropriate telemetry use based on evidence-based guidelines is essential to ensuring safe patient care.

Problem Statement

A 300-bed hospital in Southern California struggles daily with telemetry bed availability and Emergency Department to floor transfer delay. A random audit of telemetry patients on a neurosciences floor revealed that at least 20% of patients did not meet telemetry criteria. Although AHA's guidelines exist as a general hospital policy, providers do not adhere to the guidelines, and telemetry admissions are based solely on the admitting physicians' clinical decisions. Providers do not assess the patients' telemetry indication daily, and many patients remain on telemetry until discharge.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement and evaluate a provider-led daily telemetry renewal protocol based on AHA telemetry practice guidelines to decrease unnecessary telemetry use and improve alarm fatigue.

Supporting Framework

The supporting framework used for this project was the Iowa Model of Evidence Based Practice; the conceptual diagram is shown in Figure 1. Making changes to current routine healthcare practice is a difficult task that involves focused, interdisciplinary efforts. Furthermore, introducing evidence-based practices (EBP) to a community hospital requires confronting multiple implementation barriers with patients, nurses, managers, physicians, and the organization. Some of the organizational barriers are cultural factors that can determine whether a practice change can be initiated and may affect staff's willingness to participate in hospital-wide reforms (Michalec et al., 2015).

Interventions that address multi-level cultural differences in the organization prior to EBP implementation is key to ensuring its success and sustainability (Michalec et al., 2015). Implementation barriers are unique to each institute, and that understanding why research fails to translate into clinical practice is necessary prior to developing new strategies. It is therefore important to have a guiding framework that addresses implementation and considers sustainability of practice changes.

The Iowa Model of Evidence Based Practice (Figure 1), a framework developed by the University of Iowa to facilitate knowledge translation, was used for this project (Titler et al., 2001). This framework presents a realistic and detailed approach (Figure 2) and has been used successfully in many acute-care nursing QI projects (Titler et al., 2001; White & Spruce, 2015; Brown, 2014). For example, White and Spruce (2015) showed how the Iowa Model can help perioperative nurses implement practice changes to reduce surgical site infections. Haxton, Doering, Gingras, and Kelly (2012) also used the Iowa Model and successfully implemented skin-to-skin contact between neonates and new mothers in the hospital.

The Iowa framework consists of seven steps in an algorithm with decision points and feedback loops (Titler et al., 2001). The first step involves generating a topic in response to problem-based or knowledge-based triggers. Overmonitoring and alarm fatigue are knowledge-based triggers since solutions to these problems involve making clinicians aware of new information. The second step is a decision point that involves determining whether the clinical problem is a priority for the organization (Titler et al., 2001). This step was relevant for this DNP project since the target hospital is very resistant to change and buy-in from major stakeholders is the biggest facilitator to reform.

Conversations with stakeholders can reveal the hospital's major priorities, such as 1) high staff turnover due to burnout, 2) poor hospital throughput and low telemetry bed availability, 3) loud ambient noise, and 4) poor patient satisfaction. Aligning the clinical problem with organizational goals can bring immediate stakeholder buy-in, which facilitates the implementation of the DNP project.

The third step in the Iowa model involves the formation of an interdisciplinary team (Titler et al., 2001). Each discipline offers a unique perspective on the clinical problem. The telemetry taskforce for this project included the director of Cardiovascular Services and Clinical Research, the hospitalist physician lead, a cardiologist, an informatics nurse, and a nursing manager. The next two steps consist of evidence retrieval and grading (Titler et al., 2001). The AHA Practice Standards for ECG monitoring in hospital settings is a review of current best evidence, which includes recommendations from experts (cardiology, electrophysiology, interventional cardiology, hospitalists and other interdisciplinary professions). The guideline complies to AHA Level of Evidence grading algorithm, and updates periodically to reflect new evidence (Sandau et al., 2017). Since clinical trials on cardiac monitoring cannot be ethically done, this report may be the best evidence that exists.

The sixth step involves designing and piloting the practice change (Titler et al., 2001). The author created the Daily Telemetry Renewal Protocol based on AHA's risk classification system. Retrospective data was collected with the help of the informatics nurse. The providers from the hospitalist group participated in the pilot project. Results from the pilot study leads to the next decision point, the seventh and last step in which the

pilot results will be evaluated to determine whether the protocol can be adopted hospital-wide (Titler et al., 2001).

Figure 1. The Iowa Model of Evidence Based Practice (Titler et al., 2001)

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Strategies

A literature review was conducted utilizing the databases PubMed, CINAHL, and EBSCO, Google and Google Scholar. Search terms included alarm fatigue, ECG alarm management, alarm management, alarm safety, telemetry alarm fatigue. Inclusion criteria were journals published from 2013 to 2018, and in English language only. Reference lists of articles retrieved were searched for pertinent studies.

In order to find sources other than academic studies for this project, a second literature search was conducted utilizing the same databases. Resource types included journal articles, unpublished articles, conference proceedings, theses and dissertations, newspaper article, hospital-based PowerPoint education material, and reviews. Search key terms were different than the previous search and included the terms telemetry utilization, telemetry methods, over-monitoring, and practice guidelines. Inclusions were journals published after 2008 and in English. Key Mesh terms included: adverse effects, epidemiology, nursing, adherence and methods. Exclusions were studies involving children, and outpatient studies. Table 1 shows the search strategies and number of articles retrieved.

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement and evaluate a daily telemetry renewal protocol based on AHA telemetry practice guidelines to decrease unnecessary telemetry use and improve alarm fatigue. As previously discussed, alarm fatigue is a phenomenon where clinicians who are exposed to a large number of alarms become desensitized to the noises. This in turn leads to nursing behavior such as turning the alarm off or ignoring the alerts, which may result in a patient's death. The review of

evidence for this DNP project presented an overview and history of the problem, the issues that resulted and the interventions that have been evaluated to address the problem.

Table 1

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Terms	Search Term Combinations	# Found
Alarm fatigue and related interventions	ECG		436
	Patient safety	-alarm fatigue AND ECG	
	Equipment	-alarm fatigue AND patient safety	
	Nurse competence	-alarm fatigue AND equipment	
	Education	-alarm fatigue AND nurse competence	
	Telemetry overuse overmonitoring	-alarm fatigue AND education	
Telemetry	Noise	-alarm fatigue AND telemetry overuse	253
	Methods	-alarm fatigue AND overmonitoring	
	Trends	-alarm fatigue AND noise	
	Utilization	-telemetry AND methods	
	Economics	-telemetry AND trends	
	Efficiency	-telemetry AND Utilization	
	Practice Guidelines	-telemetry AND economics	
Guideline adherence	-telemetry AND efficiency		
		-telemetry AND Practice guidelines	
		-telemetry and guideline adherence	

History of Electrocardiographic Monitoring

Ischemic heart disease has been and continues to be the number one cause of death with the highest mortality rate in the U.S. (Moran et al., 2014). The development of electrocardiographic devices allowed the prompt detection and treatment of acute cardiac diseases, which led to a significant reduction in patient mortality and morbidity in the last 50 years. The use of physiological monitors first started in the operating room in the 1950s. Himmelstein and Schneier (1952) devised an instrument called the cardiotoscope that recorded and had alarms for high and low heart rates during surgeries. Thereafter, many alarm manufacturers made progressively more sophisticated

alarms such as the Electrodyne PM-65, a cardioscope pacemaker combination that reduced acute myocardial infarction mortality rate by 20% in one year in a study at a Kansas hospital in 1953 (Day, 1963). In the 1960s, central and bedside ECG monitors with features very similar to the modern device became more and more common in the clinical setting (Fentosim Clinical Inc., 2004). The invention of microprocessors in the 1980s produced real-time digitalized bedside ECG monitors; and in the 1990s, portable equipment became ubiquitous in all areas such as the emergency room, operating room and intensive care unit (Fentosim Clinical Inc., 2004).

As telemetry, or continuous ECG monitoring, became a common practice, hospitals underwent infrastructure and staffing changes accordingly. Some hospitals used bed-side ECG monitors, where others utilized centralized stations with monitor technologists who watch and report alarm events to licensed staff. In 2004, California became the first state to mandate staffing based on patient telemetry status. Title 22 of the California Code of Regulations (2004) made it mandatory for hospitals to staff at least one nurse per 4 telemetry patients.

Magnitude of the Issue

The ECG alarm was designed to be sensitive enough so that no abnormal patient cardiac event would be missed. It allowed early recognition and treatment of critical conditions, with the intention to decrease mortality and morbidity rates associated with acute coronary diseases. However, the technology that was designed to ensure patient safety has become problematic. Alarm fatigue is a major patient safety issue in hospitals all over the United States. Alarm-related patient deaths at a Boston Medical center initiated a nation-wide investigation that found 200 deaths related to alarms in 5 years

(Cvach, 2012). The resulting malpractice lawsuits and media involvement continue even until today (Logan, 2011). In 2007, the ECRI Institute listed alarm fatigue as one of the Top Ten Hazards in the medical industry (Keller, 2012). Alarm-related patient adverse events were often not recognized and frequently were underreported across all healthcare settings (The Joint Commission, 2013). From 2005 to 2012, the Food and Drug Administration (2011) found 862 deaths related to medical alarms. The Joint Commission (2013) reported 80 alarm-related deaths from 2009 to 2012. The Joint Commission made alarm safety a National Patient Safety Goal in 2014, and alarm management is currently an accreditation requirement for all acute care facilities.

Alarm credibility is the ability of the device to detect true patient events that warrant a change in current treatments, action from the nurse or other staff members, or consulting another provider. False alarms, otherwise known as non-actionable or clinically insignificant alarms, are alarms that do not correlate to a true patient event and does not lead to clinical interventions. High false alarm occurrence leads to decrease alarm credibility. Despite national efforts to combat alarm fatigue and improve alarm credibility, it continues to be a challenging issue. A high incidence of false alarms leads to inefficient use of nursing time, delayed nurse response, noise pollution, nurse burnout and most important of all, patient harm; and it occurs across all acute care settings (Albert et al., 2015; Bonafide et al., 2015; Drew et al., 2014). Bonafide et al. (2015) observed alarm occurrence for 210 hours on a medical surgical unit and found more than 5000 total alarms, of which only 1% required clinical intervention. The same study found that 100% of ECG alarms for critical arrhythmia were non-actionable. Measured nurse-response time on the medical-surgical unit showed a median response time of 9.8

minutes, almost twice the amount of time it takes for anoxic brain injury to occur (Busl & Greer, 2010). Drew et al. (2014) observed ECG alarms in five adult ICUs at a university hospital over a period of 31 days; they also found a total of 2,558,760 alarms, of which 88.8% were false. Many studies were performed with different monitoring equipment, in different settings with various staffing ratios; some units used monitor watchers, where others did not (Bonafide et al., 2015; Drew et al., 2014; Gazarian, 2014). Despite all the differences, the evidence unanimously showed a high number of non-actionable alarms in the hospital setting.

Noise Pollution

High alarm frequency, or the number of alarms that sound off during a specific period of time, leads to noise pollution in hospitals. Electrocardiographic monitor alarms are the most frequent noise in ICUs (Kinstler et al., 2015). Patients, as well as nurses can experience noise-related adverse events. According to the United States Alarm Signals Law 113.25-12, the minimum alarm tone must not be less than 80 dB, and at least 10dB higher than the background noise (Legal Information Institute, 2008). This law contradicts the World Health Organization's guidelines which suggest a maximum average noise level of 40dB at a hospital overnight (Berglund, Lindvall & Schwela, 1999). Studies on noise levels across ICUs found sound levels at least 10 dB above WHO's guidelines (Konkani, Oakley, Penprase, 2014; Simons et al., 2014; Tainter et al., 2016); studies in a burns ICU (Cordova, Logishetty, Fauerbach, Price, 2013), pediatric ICUs (Kramer, Joshi & Heard, 2016), the operating room (Katz, 2014) as well as medical surgical units (Hill & LaVela, 2015; Ryan et al., 2016) found similar results.

Nurse Burn-out and Patient Harm

Alarm noise leads to adverse patient and staff outcomes. Negative patient outcomes associated with noise pollution include 1) sleep disruptions, 2) arrhythmias in previously healthy patients, 3) delirium, 4) increased catecholamine release (Munzel et al., 2014), 5) high oxygen demand, 6) delayed wound healing (Hsu, Ryherd, Persson, & Ackerman, 2012), 7) increased surgical site infections (Dholakia et al., 2015), 8) high APACHE II scores (Park et al., 2015), 9) increased length of stay (Salluh et al., 2010), and 10) increased readmission rates (Hagerman et al, 2005). When the hospital noise was loud, patients were also less able to understand speech (Pope, Guallun & Kampel, 2013) and often perceived staff performance as poor (Hasfeldt, Maindal, Toft & Birkelund, 2014).

Occupational exposure to noise levels above 75 dB also leads to unamenable health consequences such as permanent hearing loss (Basner et al, 2014), cardiovascular diseases (Munzel et al., 2014; Vienneau et al., 2015), and even permanent disability (Kim, 2007). Nurses with noise-induced stress also experience agitation, distraction, anxiety, burnout and poor work performance (Davidson et al., 2015; World Health Organization: European Commission, 2015). Responding to frequent false alarms can affect the clinician's concentration, mental capacity and cognition. Alarms interrupt nursing workflow and lead to increased risk of medical errors (Kiymaz & Koc, 2017).

Causes of False Alarms and Interventions

It is important to look at causes to assess the causes of false alarms prior to an evaluation of alarm management interventions. The following section will look at factors that cause clinically insignificant ECG alarms in the hospital setting. These factors

include overmonitoring, artifact secondary to patient movement, lack of individualized patient parameters, and equipment failure.

Overmonitoring

Overmonitoring involves the utilization of telemetry services on patients without an indication supported by the AHA telemetry practice guidelines. Overmonitoring is the biggest contributing factor to the overall alarm burden. Monitoring patients with low cardiovascular risk (normal initial ECGs, normal cardiac markers) has little benefit to patient outcomes (Perkins et al., 2014). Hospitals' widespread non-adherence to AHA telemetry practice guidelines (Figure 1) resulted in a culture of ECG overmonitoring (Chen et al., 2017). Many patients with non-cardiac primary diagnoses were placed on telemetry simply due to the acuity of the primary diagnosis (Crawford & Halm, 2015). The AHA telemetry practice guidelines were derived from expert opinions. Although it may be the best existing empirical evidence on managing telemetry practice, it lacks convincibility when compared to evidence from randomized controlled trials. Many researchers expressed mixed emotions toward the guidelines; some regard it as the gold standard (Chen et al., 2017; Funk et al, 2017) while others criticize it as incomprehensive and unsafe (Dhillon et al, 2009). Studies showed that most providers who utilize telemetry inappropriately were unaware of the AHA telemetry practice guidelines (Johnson et al., 2016; Sharma et al., 2016; Svec et al., 2015). Data from numerous clinical trials showed that up to 40% of hospitalized patients on continuous telemetry protocols did not meet monitoring criteria (Chen et al., 2017; Dressler et al., 2014; Ramkumar et al., 2017).

Adherence to AHA practice guidelines in different hospital settings have shown up to 70% reduction in telemetry days and an average of 9 minutes per patient per day reduction of alarm-related nursing time (Alsaad et al., 2017). Interventions to improve AHA practice guidelines adherence include mandatory policies, Electronic Medical Record (EMR) system auto-discontinuation (Dressler et al., 2014), EMR reminders (Rizvi et al., 2017), provider education, and multidisciplinary nurse-led telemetry discontinuation protocols (Crimlisk, Johnstone & Winter, 2015; Patel, Sim & Dowling, 2016; Perrin et al., 2017).

Most studies showed significant post-intervention reductions in telemetry duration and overall alarm burden (Dressler et al., 2014; Patel, Sim & Dowling, 2016; Svec et al., 2015). Nurse-led interventions faced less resistance and tended to be more sustained than physician-based practice changes. Nurses lacked confidence in making independent decisions regarding telemetry status and were willing to abide by guidelines (Christensen et al., 2014). When faced with so many false alarms, and accuracy in rhythm interpretation and patient assessment is crucial. Without organizational practice guidelines, meaningful use of alarms and patient safety is completely dependent on practitioner competence (Sowan et al., 2017). A descriptive study found that nurses with fewer years of ICU experience ignored alarms more often and were less able to detect true patient deterioration when responding to alarms (Despins, 2017). Therefore, having a clear telemetry protocol based on AHA practice guidelines can decrease inconsistent nursing judgement in response to critical alerts. A few studies found that although physician-based interventions initially improved adherence, many physicians were resistant and re-ordered telemetry post discontinuation (Boggan et al., 2014; Leighton,

Kianfar, Serynek & Kerwin, 2013). One study had to provide financial incentives to physicians in order to ensure compliance (Svec et al., 2015).

Continuous ECG monitoring gives providers a false sense of safety. Providers, especially residents, lack adequate ECG interpretation skills (Salerno, Alguire & Waxman, 2003), and may rely on continuous telemetry rather than episodic ECGs to manage patients' illnesses. More studies on causes of physicians' reluctance to comply with AHA telemetry practice guidelines need to be done in order to produce effective physician-based alarm-management interventions.

Artifact and Alarm Parameters

Patient movement, positioning and poor placement of ECG leads cause artifact alarms. Drew et al. (2014) found that 9% of false ECG alarms were related to poor alarm signal due to lead attachment issues. Current literature showed that the use of disposable electrodes, daily electrode changes and proper skin preparation consistently reduced false technical alarms (Garcia, Haney, Kaplan & Staton, 2014; Hannibal, 2014; Walsh-Irwin & Jurgens, 2015). False positive alarms, or "true" alarms that require no clinical actions often sound due to wide monitoring parameters. Individualizing parameters to each patient's clinical condition reduced non-actionable alarms (Sowan et al., 2016). The main causes of false positive alarms include chronic atrial fibrillation, PVCs, short ST elevations, low and wide amplitude QRS complexes, and pacemaker rhythms (Drew et al., 2014). Patient characteristics were the key determinants to alarm adjustments needed to prevent false alarms (Drew et al., 2014; Harris et al., 2017). For instance, altering QRS complex parameters in obese patients and lowering HR parameters in clinically-stable heart block patients reduced a significant amount of alarms in respective patient

populations (Drew et al., 2014). In addition, nurses perceive the lack of alarm parameter adjustments to be the main cause of false positive alarms in the acute care setting (Christensen et al., 2014). Allan, Doyle, Sapirstein and Cvach (2017) reduced overall ECG alarms by 61% in a cardiovascular ICU by implementing alarm adjustments such as adding delays to default thresholds. The Healthcare Technology Safety Institute found a 40% reduction in alarms by allowing nurses to adjust alarm parameters (ECRI Institute, 2015). Even though all types and brands of ECG alarms allowed individualization of parameters, it was often not done due to lack of staff training on alarm functions, unwillingness of nurses to change settings without physicians' approval, and staffing (Scruth, 2014). A combination of previously mentioned interventions produced even more significant results in eliminating false ECG alarms. Sendelbach et al. (2015) implemented a bundle intervention that included alarm parameter customization, daily electrode changes and skin preparation; results showed an 88.5% reduction of false alarms. However, the authors also recognized that the increase in nursing workload related to the bundle intervention was great, and that the sustainability of practice changes may be problematic.

Alarm Failures

Alarm technology is constantly being upgraded. Some alarm manufacturers have completely revamped their monitoring products to combat alarm fatigue. A review by Nizami et al. (2013) found that most ECG alarm algorithms came from a limited dataset that does not reflect what actually occurs on real hospital units. Therefore, it is important for manufacturers to base alarm algorithms on larger datasets collected from real clinical settings (Clifford et al., 2015). Technological changes that improved alarm credibility

included software modules that combined analysis of rhythms with other physiological parameters such as arterial blood pressure and pulsatile waveforms (Ansari et al., 2015; Couto et al., 2015; Krasteva et al., 2016); these studies derived various complex software suggestions with inconsistent results. Technology-based interventions usually required purchase of new software or alarm systems and is the least realistic intervention for hospitals due to cost.

Limitations

Acute care ECG alarm management is a complex problem that cannot be resolved by approaches that focus on a single dimension. An on-going multidisciplinary approach that addresses all aspects of patient care is needed to restore meaningful use of ECG alarms and produce sustained results. Kurka et al. (2014) found that identification of clinically relevant alarms required manual reviews of all alarms; this almost defeated the purpose of an automated alarm system since it required so much manpower. A systematic review by Yue, Plummer & Cross (2017) showed that although employer-supported nurse education produced statistically significant reductions in false alarm frequency, the results were not sustained. Similarly, another study by Sowan et al. (2016) found that although individualizing patient alarm parameters reduced false alarms, it did not improve overall alarm safety in the complex ICU environment. Although different approaches to ECG alarm management showed promising results, further research and ongoing organizational investment are needed to identify best ways to measure and reduce alarm fatigue.

METHODS

This quality improvement project's aim was to design, implement and evaluate a daily telemetry renewal protocol for a 300-bed community hospital in Southern California. The assessment was used daily by physicians for all patients currently on telemetry, either to terminate or continue telemetry monitoring.

Setting

The project took place on a telemetry unit at a 300-bed acute care facility in Southern California. The hospital is a primary stroke center with a total of four adult geriatric telemetry units (cardiac, respiratory, surgical and neurosciences). Each unit has the maximum capacity of 36 telemetry patients. The units have central monitoring stations and use one trained personnel per unit who acts as a medical secretary and monitor watcher each shift. The unit averages 28 to 36 patients per day and is often at full capacity. The neurosciences unit admits patients with diagnosis such as stroke, encephalopathy, chronic neuromuscular diseases, and other miscellaneous medical diagnosis. These patients usually receive treatment and stabilize in the ICU for at least 48 hours prior to transferring to the neurosciences unit. There are also diagnosis specific criteria that warrant direct patient transfer into the ICU if needed. The hospital employs a hospitalist group of providers to manage a subset of their total patients. The hospitalist group uses three providers per shift to medically manage approximately 50 patients from 7 am to 7 pm, and one physician from 7pm to 7am. All patients with telemetry orders remain on telemetry until orders are discontinued by a provider.

Ethical Considerations

Permission to proceed with this quality improvement project was granted by the Chief Nursing Officer of the organization, and IRB approval was obtained from the hospital as well as from California State University Los Angeles. All participating staff members gave informed consent, and all patient data was de-identified.

Participants

Project participants included providers who belonged to the hospitalist group. The participants included both physicians and nurse practitioners. The physicians are responsible for admitting new patients, inputting admitting orders and supervising the clinical care of all patients, while the nurse practitioners are focused on patients with lower acuity.

Project Process

The following section outlines the steps in which the telemetry protocol was developed, implemented and evaluated.

Step One: Retrospective Data Analysis of Telemetry Utilization

The author first looked at historical telemetry utilization data to determine which unit to focus the project on. Telemetry utilization in this project was defined as the percentage of patients out of the total number of patients on the unit with an active telemetry order. Patient census is the number of total inpatients admitted at the hospital each day; telemetry census refers to the number of patients with an active telemetry order. All patient census and telemetry census from September 1st, 2017 to January 1st, 2018 were collected and analyzed. The author summarized the census data by hospital unit and date. The retrospective data analysis allowed the author to identify the unit with

the highest telemetry utilization, the neurosciences floor. This unit was then selected with approval from the hospital as the location where the author's quality improvement project was to take place.

Step Two: Development of Daily Telemetry Renewal Order Sheet

The Daily Telemetry Renewal Order Sheet was developed by the author based on AHA's criteria for telemetry indication. The specific criteria included in the protocol were customized to fit the clinical characteristics of patients who are commonly admitted to the selected unit. For instance, all criteria that pertain to the ICU were excluded. The protocol was approved by the leading hospitalist physicians as well as the lead cardiologist prior to implementation. The order sheet included a succinct summary of AHA's classification system. The purpose of the order sheet was to guide the provider in determining whether each patient meets telemetry criteria on a daily basis (Appendix A).

Step Three: Retrospective Data Presentation

The retrospective data analysis revealed the days with the highest telemetry utilization on the neurosciences unit. In order to determine whether the high telemetry utilization on those days were due to indicated patient conditions according to AHA's telemetry guidelines, the author reviewed the records of patients who were admitted under the hospitalist group on those days. Each patient was assessed for telemetry indication using the author's protocol. The author then presented the results of the assessment to hospital leadership and the providers from the hospitalist group. The author was able to obtain informed consent from hospitalist providers after the presentation prior to implementation of the quality improvement project.

Step Four: Implementation

The protocol was implemented on the neurosciences unit for 15 days. Each day, a Daily Telemetry Renewal Order Sheet (Appendix A) was placed in the chart for participating providers to complete. When the attending clinician (physician or nurse practitioner) did not agree to discontinue telemetry for a patient who met discontinuation criteria, a rationale was required. The author was onsite and available to answer any questions the providers had regarding the protocol. The lead hospital cardiologist was available for consultation via telephone from 9:00 am to 9:30 pm during implementation days. The author collected all order sheets at the end of each day and recorded findings.

Step Five: Safety Monitoring

The author monitored and documented any actionable cardiac event after every patient received telemetry discontinuation orders. Events that qualified as actionable cardiac events were those that required 1) reinstatement of telemetry, 2) a rapid response, or 3) upgrade to a higher acuity level.

Measures

All patient data and provider responses were de-identified and recorded electronically by the author, and all data were stored in a password protected computer. All paper records were stored in a locked cabinet on the unit only accessible to the author.

The Protocol

The Daily Telemetry Renewal Order Sheet (Appendix A) helped practitioners identify whether a patient met the indication for continuous cardiac monitoring according

to AHA’s telemetry practice guidelines. During implementation days, the author recorded daily findings electronically on the daily data collection sheet (Figure 2).

Daily Data Collection sheet																										
Date:																										
Pt #:	Age	Gender	LOS	Insurance	Primary Diagnosis	AVB	ACS	AHF	LQS	WPW	SHH	TDP	AS	CPS	AMT	SYN	RCA	AAT	AAN	SHF	RAH	NCE	NCP	Tele Status	fit crit for DC?	Rationale

Figure 2. Daily data collection sheet.

RESULTS

Retrospective Data Period

Patient Characteristics

In the review of chart data to identify the highest days of utilization and the unit, there were 27 patients identified in the retrospective patient sample on the three highest days of telemetry utilization. The average age for these 27 patients was 68 ($SD = 22.69$), and age ranged from 24 to 105 years. There were 17 females (63%) and 10 males (37%). The average length of stay was 5.6 days ($SD = 8.6$) and ranged from 1 to 30 days. Two patients were uninsured, and both of them were under 65 years. Eighteen out of 27 (67%) patients who were being monitored did not meet the criteria for continuous telemetry monitoring, based on the protocol. Frequencies and percentages of patient characteristics are displayed in Table 2.

Prospective Data Period

Patient Characteristics

The author implemented the daily telemetry renewal protocol on a total of 155 patients over 15 days. The average age of the patients was 64 years ($SD = 19.03$), and age ranged from 28 to 99 years. There were 65 females (41.93%) and 89 males (57.7%). The average length of stay was 5.1 days ($SD = 4.88$) and ranged from 1 to 23 days. Eleven patients (5.8%) were uninsured and all of them were under the age of 65. Frequencies and percentages are displayed in Table 2. A t-test was performed on age for the two patient groups (retrospective/prospective data period), and no significant difference was found, $p=0.3588$.

For each day of the project, the percentage of patients not meeting the telemetry protocol criteria ranged from 14% to 56%. The physicians were then given the protocol and asked to reevaluate the patient's need for telemetry. After the re-evaluation, some patients had their telemetry orders discontinued. On day 2, 12, and 13, patients being monitored before and after the physicians reassessment did not change. The average decrease in telemetry utilization was 17.9% ($SD = 14.85$) and ranged from 8% to 45%. The percentages and frequencies are displayed in Table 3.

Table 2

Patient Characteristics

		Retrospective Data Period	Prospective Data Period
		Frequency (%) N = 27	Frequency (%) N = 155
Gender	Female	41.93	63
	Male	57.70	37
Age *	18-29	0.64	7
	30-39	17.5	4
	40-49	7.79	7
	50-59	18.8	19
	60-69	10.9	27
	70-79	14.2	7.4
	80-89	18.1	7.4
	90-99	9.67	18.5
	100-109	0	7.4
Insurance	Medicare only	42	26
	Medicare & Medicaid	6.5	33
	Commercial (HMO & PPO)	3.2	0
	Medicaid only	42.2	33
	Self-pay	5.8	7
Length of stay	0-3 (days)	53.2	63
	4-6	22.1	26
	7+	24.7	11

* *t*-test, $p = 0.3588$

Table 3

Response to Daily Telemetry Renewal Protocol

Implementation Day	Pts who did not meet monitoring criteria before protocol implementation (%)	Pts who did not meet monitoring criteria after protocol implementation (%)	Difference in telemetry utilization (%) *
1	56	11	45
2	22	22	0
3	30	10	20
4	28.57	14	14.57
5	50	10	40
6	25	12.5	12.5
7	50	10	40
8	25	17	8
9	46.15	15.3	30.85
10	45.45	36.3	9.15
11	50	30	20
12	18	18	0
13	14.3	14.3	0
14	28.47	14	14.47
15	24	10	14

* *t*-test, $p = 0.0005$

Figure 3. Patients on telemetry not meeting protocol criteria before and after protocol implementation

Provider Rationale

According to the author’s protocol, providers who chose not to discontinue telemetry were asked to provide a rationale. In total, 26 patients met telemetry discontinuation criteria according to the protocol but did not receive discontinuation orders from their providers (Figure 5). Age was the number one rationale providers used to justify their decisions. All patients who received age as a rationale for telemetry renewal were over 80 years old , and their diagnoses include neutropenia, cellulitis of the lower extremities, colitis and acute renal failure.

Eight patients who did not meet criteria were kept on telemetry due to the rationale of “agitation”; all patients were admitted with medical diagnoses but had secondary psychiatric or substance abuse disorders. Six patients with the admitting diagnosis of anemia remained on telemetry due to a physician rationale of “anemia”. One 44-year-old female patient with acute cystitis received telemetry renewal with the provider rationale “leukocytosis”.

Figure 4. Physician rationale for telemetry renewal for patient not meeting protocol criteria.

DISCUSSION

This DNP project implemented a protocol to renew telemetry monitoring in accordance with AHA's telemetry practice guidelines. Unnecessary cardiac monitoring is costly, causes alarm fatigue which makes clinicians prone to medical errors and burnout (Keller, 2012; Whalen et al., 2014). Organizations face a shortage of telemetry beds daily, and physician groups must appropriately manage telemetry use to continue to provide a sustainable service. Cardiac monitoring needs to be assessed on a daily basis by a medical provider. The daily protocol implementation resulted in fewer monitored patients and also identified some of the rationales that physicians use to justify continuing monitoring. Identification of provider rationale for telemetry renewal can help organizations explore other more appropriate and cost-effective ways to monitor patients.

Age was the number one rationale providers used for renewing telemetry for patients who did not meet protocol criteria. Geriatric patients as compared to the general population have a higher cardiovascular risk profile that necessitates continuous cardiac monitoring (Ali & Grossman, 2017). A scientific statement from the AHA indicated that current evidence-based diagnosis and treatment recommendations are not tailored to patients over the age of 75 because this patient group has been largely underrepresented in cardiovascular trials (Rich et al., 2016). It is the lack of evidence to guide telemetry clinical decision making in the geriatric population that results in overmonitoring of patients over the age of 75; future research is needed to close the knowledge gaps to resolve this issue.

In this project, patients with psychiatric secondary diagnosis and behavioral issues received telemetry renewal orders because their activities needed to be monitored. One

physician kept a patient on telemetry because she had a history of seizures and was hospitalized for encephalopathy. Another 34-year-old female patient admitted for alcohol-induced pancreatitis and delirium had been on telemetry for 8 days; the physician who renewed her telemetry orders indicated that putting this patient on telemetry would “at least make sure someone hears her when she gets out of bed”. Activity monitoring can be performed by a trained certified nurse’s assistant stationed at the bedside, who not only can better ensure the patient’s safety but also may be a more cost-effective alternative to daily cardiac monitoring.

Two other common physician rationales were anemia and leukocytosis, which do not have a direct correlation to cardiac status. In the author’s project, clinical laboratory data showed that all six “anemia” patients had hemoglobin levels between 8-9 g/dl. Hospital medical records showed that the white blood cells of the “leukocytosis” patient was 12,000 cells/microliter. Without any other cardiac risks, continuous cardiac monitoring may not be the appropriate way to ensure patient safety in these patient cases.

Reducing telemetry usage using the AHA’s guidelines is a safe practice. A retrospective analysis of rapid response team and code events after a telemetry reduction project showed that there were no differences between the preintervention, intervention and postintervention period (Xie et al., 2018). During the implementation of this project, there were no patient safety events identified during or after the author’s project implementation period.

The implementation of the daily telemetry renewal protocol among the hospitalists at this community hospital showed a statistically significant decrease in the overall telemetry utilization not meeting AHA’s telemetry guidelines. The providers

offered the feedback that the protocol was simple to use and they were easily able to make guided clinical decisions. The hospitalist group grades all providers based on length of stay, readmission rates and telemetry utilization, therefore each provider is motivated to reduce telemetry usage. Currently, patient telemetry orders are automatically renewed each day. The group suggested switching telemetry renewal to a daily process, and also incorporating it into the Electronic Medical Records (EMR) system so that all providers receive a daily reminder. Following the guidance of the Iowa's Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care, the next step is to evaluate the outcomes of this project and disseminate the results hospital-wide. The most effective way to disseminate this project's results is to incorporate the author's daily telemetry renewal protocol into the EMR system to influence telemetry utilization in more patients.

There were many limitations to this quality improvement project. The author was only able to implement the protocol for 15 days; a longer testing period is needed to evaluate the effect of the author's protocol on telemetry practice among providers at this hospital. Patient safety is very important, and a longer implementation period can help identify any potential patient adverse events related to telemetry discontinuation using the author's protocol. Also, only providers from a hospitalist group participated in this project; this hospitalist group rewards providers for low telemetry utilization therefore all providers had incentives to evaluate telemetry use daily. This may not be the case for another hospitalist group or independent physicians who may not have the same practice restrictions and incentives as physicians who belong to the hospitalist group in this DNP project.

Implications for Practice

The findings from this quality improvement project demonstrated that a protocol for providers designed to revisit the need for daily monitoring can reduce overmonitoring in acute care settings. Quality improvement projects, especially at academic centers have focused on nurse-led interventions to reduce alarm fatigue. Some nurse-based projects involved daily electrode placement, skin preparation (Walsh-Irwin & Jurgens, 2015), adjustment of default alarm settings and nursing education on monitor use (Sowen et al., 2016). These projects added many tasks to the nurse's routine and were not sustainable solutions; nurses also indicated that the education provided was insufficient for them to safely adjust the monitors (Sowen et al., 2016).

Some projects implemented nurse-led telemetry discontinuation protocols to reduce overmonitoring, and participating nurses expressed a lack of confidence in decision making (Perrin et al., 2017; Glenn, 2019). Cardiac monitoring is a decision that needs to be made by a provider to ensure patient safety. This project demonstrated that a provider-initiated telemetry reduction protocol is possible. It is also more likely to be sustained, especially if it can be incorporated into the EMR System. Rizvi et al. (2017) implemented an EMR pop-up reminder for discontinuing telemetry for patients who no longer met criteria in three regional hospitals; the results showed a reduction of telemetry utilization by 37%. If the author's the protocol can be built into the hospital's EMR system with a daily pop-up reminder for telemetry renewal, the process can be automated and telemetry reduction can be sustained.

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APPENDIX

PHYSICIAN DAILY TELEMETRY RENEWAL ORDER SHEET

Physician Daily Telemetry Renewal Order Sheet

The American Heart Association's Telemetry Practice Guidelines recommend Continuous Telemetry Monitoring according to criteria based on a Class System as follows. (The guidelines have been modified to fit the population on 3N)

Telemetry Renewal Recommended:

CLASS I	2nd and 3rd degree AV block Acute Coronary Syndrome with high grade lesion awaiting intervention Acute heart failure/pulmonary edema Long QT syndrome Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome with rapid anterograde conduction Severe hypokalemia or hypomagnesemia Administration of antiarrhythmic drugs known to cause torsade de pointes Acute stroke (48 hours)
CLASS II	Chest pain syndromes Presence of arrhythmia with active arrhythmia medication titration Syncope At risk for cardiac arrest, respiratory arrest, or development of hypotension

Telemetry **Discontinuation** recommended:

CLASS III	Absence of arrhythmia for 48 hours 48 hours after acute neurological event (syncope, stroke) without arrhythmias Clinical stabilization of acute decompensated heart failure Resolution of arrhythmias by medical therapy or device Negative cardiac enzymes and stress test in chest pain patients No further chest pain in uncomplicated MI patients (under observation for 2-4 days post MI)
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Physician Orders:

	Discontinue telemetry (no telemetry needs identified)
	Continue telemetry Rationale (list diagnosis):

Telemetry Renewal Recommended:

Name: _____ Signature: _____

Patient Label	Date: _____
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